

Assessment of Physicochemical Properties of Soil at Fadama Lands in Southeastern Nigeria

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Received: January, 30, 2026; Accepted: February 5, 2026; Published: June 6, 2026

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20570520>

Abstract: Fadama soils have the capability to produce crops on a sustainable basis but are vulnerable to deterioration due to their fragile nature. This research was carried out to evaluate the physicochemical status of five Fadama soils across Southeast Nigeria (Oguta, Bende, Ihiala, Adani and Akaeze). Five (5) samples each for auger and core soils were randomly collected from each location, and were processed and sent for laboratory determinations. Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance, while significant means were separated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference at 5% level of probability. Results obtained showed high sand fractions (>70%) followed by silt and clay. The soil pH was (5.75-6.19) moderately acidic: Nitrogen (0.11-0.25%) and available phosphorous (3.52 – 14.47 mg/kg) were moderate. Potassium (0.108-0.825 cmol/kg) organic matter (0.86-9.02%) and exchange potassium (0.10-1.84 cmol/kg) effective cation exchange capacity were all above critical values, showing that fadama soils of Southeastern Nigeria have great potentials for crop production. However, the fadama soils of Southeastern Nigeria are predominantly sandy and could limit soil productivity; hence, agricultural conservation practices such as mulching, organic farming and crop rotation can help to enhance their productivity.

Keywords: *Properties, Fadama, sustainable crop production, southeast, physicochemical*

1.0 Introduction

High annual rainfall and numerous rivers and tributaries in some areas have combined to give rise to wide spread occurrence of flood plain soils otherwise called Fadama soils in the landscape of south east Nigeria. The term Fadama is used to describe low-lying areas including stream channels and streams referred to as alluvial low lands (FAO, 1991) that are waterlogged or flooded in wet season (Turner, 2003). They are poorly drained, fine texture and more fertile than upland soils (Babaji, 2003). They have high level of moisture in any season of the year and are classified as hydromorphic soils. They are also known for high cation exchange capacity, organic matter, available phosphorous (P), Total Nitrogen (N) and micro nutrients than upland soils (Singh, 2003). These attributes make Fadama soils very attractive for food cultivation. Due to their long time retention of moisture all year round, Fadama soils are considered suitable for cultivation of crops, and because they receive water from both natural and human sources, which impact on cleansing polluted water, recharging underground aquifers, they resist the risk of flood and drought. Fadama soils, with few exceptions are

potentially productive and suitable for intensive wet and dry land uses because of favourable soil water balance, long growing seasons, and large land unit with gently sloped to flat topography and moderate to high fertility status enhanced by the soil hydromorphic processes than their adjacent upland soils (Ogban & Babalola, 2009). Also, Fadama soils have been reported to be fragile ecosystem and their conversion to cropland may result in severe ecological and environmental degradation if not properly done (Babalola *et. al.*, 2011).

Therefore appropriate and adequate utilization of Fadama soils require detailed studies of the properties of the soils to highlight their limiting characteristics and proffer correct measures. Exploring and evaluation of soil physico-chemical properties can greatly influence our decisions on how to increase or revamp the fertility, quality and productivity of the Fadama soils. The study therefore aimed to investigate the physicochemical status of major Fadama soils in the Southeast Nigeria with the view to providing relevant information for its sustainable exploitation for crop production in the Southeast Agroecological zone of Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Method

2.1 The Study Area

The research work was conducted in five Fadama locations in Southeast Nigeria, namely Oguta, Bende, Ihiala, Adani and Akaeze. Southeast is situated between Latitudes 4.47° to 7.7°N and Longitudes 7.54° to 8.27°E coordinates, within the tropical rain forest mixed with forest savannah of Nigeria. The temperature of these locations varies from about 38°C-39°C and mean annual rainfall of 1,500mm – 2,500mm. Relative humidity ranges between 75%- 90% in the rainy season and drops to about 50% - 60% during the dry season. The study locations are characterized with poorly drained soils, with gently sloped to plain terrain. The vegetation is predominantly the secondary rainforest, and the current land use practices include the cultivation of yam, cassava, maize, rice (Merem, 2019).

2.2 Experimental design and Soil Sampling

The experiment was a field research involving free observation by random sampling of soil. Here, soils of five (5) study locations were randomly sampled at five (5) observational points in each location. The five observational points in each location served as the replicates;

hence, total of five (5) samples each for auger and core soils were obtained from each study location. The sampled areas were determined by the slope, soil type, and cropping history of the areas. This was carried out in all the five locations. The auger and core soil samples were collected at the depths of 0-30, at five (5) replicates each for the five locations. Therefore, total of twenty five (25) samples each for auger and core soils were collected for the study. Soil samples collected were bagged, properly labeled and taken to a laboratory for the determination of physical and chemical properties.

2.3 Laboratory Procedures

The Particle Size distribution of the soil samples was determined following Bouyoucons hydrometer method as outlined in Gee and Or (2002). Moisture content was determined using gravimetric method outlined in Amanze et al. (2024) and calculated as shown in Eq. 1.

$$\% \text{ MC} = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_3 - W_1} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots \text{Eq 1}$$

Where % MC = Percentage moisture content

W1 = weight of empty can

W2 = weight of air dried soil plus moisture can

W3 = weight of oven dried soil plus moisture can

Soil pH was obtained using a pH meter in soil solution ratio of 1:2.5, calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) were determined using the EDTA titration method, while sodium and potassium (K) was determined using flame photometer (Black *et.al*, 1965). Total Nitrogen was analyzed using micro – Kjeldahl technique, organic carbon was determined by Nelson and Sommers (1996).while organic matter was calculated by multiplying the value of organic carbon with 1.724. Available phosphorous was determined by

extraction using Bray 2 method of Bray and Kurt as described by Udo *et.al*, (2009).

2.4 Data analyses

Data obtained from laboratory analyses were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS analytical software version 23. Significant means were separated using Fisher’s Least Significant Difference at 5% probability level.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Some physical properties of the soils

The soils varied significantly ($P \leq 5\%$) different in particle size distribution and moisture content.

Table 1: Physical properties of Fadama soils in Southeastern part of Nigeria

Sites	Parameter (%)				Texture	Moisture
	Sand	Silt	Clay			
Adani	70.73	15.29	13.98		SL	21.40
Bende	71.38	13.38	15.27		SL	23.50
Akaeze	79.22	4.57	16.21		SL	24.00
Oguta	93.03	2.24	4.73		LS	23.00
Ihiala	88.20	2.20	9.60		LS	22.50

The particle size distribution, soil texture and moisture content of the soils are shown in Table 1. Sand particles are in the range of 70.73-93.03%, silt was in the range of 2.20% - 15.29%, while 9.60 – 16.21% was recorded for clay, which

indicates dominance of sand fractions in the areas. Texture ranged from sandy loam in Adani, sandy loam in Bende and Akaeze, to loamy sand in Oguta and Ihiala. The sandy and sandy loam nature of the soil samples is an indication that they are

vulnerable to erosion, leaching, and excessive drainage. This condition would require intensification of agronomic practices necessary for improved soil condition for effective cultivation of crops (Nweke *et . al* 2025).

3.2 Some chemical properties of the soils

The chemical properties of the Fadama soils (Table 2) showed that there was

significant ($P \leq 5\%$) variation in some chemical properties of soils at the varying Fadama Agricultural lands. The soil pH values of the Fadama soils ranged from 5.75-6.19, indicating that the soils were moderately acidic. This implies that the soils could support the cultivation of arable crops (Rediet.al, 2016).

Table 2: Chemical Properties of Fadama soils in Southeastern part of Nigeria

Sites	pH (H ₂ O)	OM (%)	(cmol/kg)						TEB	TEA	ECEC	BS (%)
			TN (%)	Av P (mg/kg)	K	Ca	Mg	Na				
Adani	5.75	5.04	0.14	14.47	0.34	9.24	3.41	0.14	13.14	1.93	15.08	87.13
Bende	6.19	4.91	0.15	12.80	0.82	26.51	8.37	2.34	38.05	2.25	40.80	93.26
Akaeze	5.18	8.49	0.25	10.97	0.40	7.06	0.35	0.08	1.60	1.72	13.32	68.19
Ihiala	5.34	3.45	0.11	11.62	0.80	11.33	4.65	0.32	17.10	1.18	18.29	93.49
Oguta	5.91	2.38	0.11	3.52	0.38	6.43	2.27	0.20	5.11	0.68	5.79	88.26

Where; OM is organic matter, TN is total nitrogen, AvP is available phosphorus, TEB is total exchangeable bases, TEA is total exchangeable acidity, ECEC is effective cation exchange capacity

The moderate acidity may be attributed to high annual rainfall that resulted in the loss of exchangeable bases through leaching and increasing Al³⁺ and H⁺ activity in the soil solution that increase soil acidity (Rediet.al, 2016). The Fadama soils studied also showed high organic matter contents in the range of 2.38 – 8.49%. The result implies that organic matter content

of the Fadama soils is generally high. Low TN contents which ranged from 0.11 – 0.25% was recorded at the five locations, which may be attributed to continuous leaching resulting from seasonal flooding which may lead to anaerobic conditions. The available phosphorous level in all the soils was low to moderate, and the lowest value (3.52 mg/kg) was obtained at the

Oguta Fadama soil. The critical value of available phosphorous is 15mg/kg, suggesting that the soils are deficient in available phosphorus. Consequently, these areas can only be sustainable for crop production using phosphorous fertilizer application. Phosphorous is referred to as the most important element in soil quality. It enhances growth, cell division, fruit development and early maturity (Umeri, 2017).

Exchangeable K of the soil samples ranged from 0.34-0.82 cmol/kg. Values in the range of 0.3-0.6 cmol/kg are classified as medium and values above 0.20 cmol/100g are considered high. This finding is an indication that the exchangeable K levels are similar to the threshold level and, therefore sufficient for crop production with minimal addition of potassium fertilization or none. The presence of K in the soil is enhanced by the solvent actions of carbonic acid, humus and acid clays (Redi et.al; 2016). Exchangeable Cations were higher than the critical value (2.0 cmol/kg). Magnesium value obtained from the study locations were in the range of 0.35 – 8.37cmol/kg. This recorded magnesium from the locations could be classified as low-high. Exchangeable Na ranged from 0.14-2.34.

This shows that Na varies in location indicating that some locations need improvement in Na for soil aggregation and improve in soil structure and prevent dispersion of clay in certain soils. The effective cation Exchange Capacity (ECEC) recorded for the soil samples in research ranged from 5.79 - 40.80 cmol/kg which varied significantly from one location to the other. Accordingly, soils with ECEC value above 4 cmol/kg are capable of withstanding heavy leaching (Chukwu *et al.*, 2009). Relatively, the five locations evaluated may likely sustain heavy leaching. ECEC is a measure of the soil's capacity to hold positive charged ions. It is responsible for soil structural stability, nutrient accessibility, soil hydrogen content (pH) and reactions of soil to fertilizers (Chukwu *et al.*, 2009). Consequently, the Fadama soils could be notable for good nutrient accessibility and fertilizer response, though the soil at Oguta would be relatively poor in these qualities.

4.0 Conclusion

The research study evaluated the physicochemical properties of five (5) Agricultural Fadama lands in the eastern part of Nigeria. Results indicated that sand particles with sandy loam texture

dominate the five sites with proportional moisture contents, indicating vulnerability to erosion and excessive drainage. Agricultural conservation practices such as mulching, organic farming and crop rotation can help to enhance their moisture retention and maintenance. All the locations were found to be moderately acidic, suggesting available nutrient and high microbial activities. Nitrogen and phosphorus fall below their critical values while organic matter, calcium, potassium and magnesium levels fall above their critical values suggesting sustained crop production without application of these fertilizers. The effective cation exchange capacities of Fadama soils at the five locations are above the critical value.

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